

On the Ethyl and Methyl Esters of Fluocarbonic Acid.

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Search for the literature shows that free halogenocarbonic acids have not been isolated, only the ethyl and methyl esters of chlorocarbonic acid being known.

Moissan (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1891, iii, 5, 456) introduced silver fluoride as the fluorinating agent. Meslans (*compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 1020) obtained acetyl fluoride by the action of anhydrous zinc fluoride on acetyl chloride. Swarts (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1930, 39, 444)* introduced SbF_5 and a small quantity of SbCl_5 or bromine (as catalyst) as well as Hg_2F_2 as fluorinating agents. The affinity of fluorine for carbon is enormous which is demonstrated by the remarkable stability of the covalent linkages of these two atoms. Fluocarbonic esters are, therefore, expected to be quite stable. Attempts to prepare the fluocarbonic esters from the corresponding chlorocarbonic esters with any of the above methods were unsuccessful, explosive decomposition with the evolution of alkyl fluoride taking place.

On the other hand, by the action of anhydrous thalious fluoride on the ethyl and methyl esters of chlorocarboic acid we have been able to isolate the corresponding fluocarbonic esters. They are pungent smelling liquids, lachrymatory, boiling respectively at 57° (ethyl ester) and 40° (methyl ester). In the absence of moisture they do not attack glass.

The substitution of chlorine by fluorine lowers the boiling point by 36° and 32° in case of ethyl and methyl esters. The methyl ester is found to be denser than the ethyl ester, the same being the case with the initial chlorocarbonic esters. It is interesting to compare the boiling points of the acid chlorides and acid fluorides previously described in the literature.

		B.p.	Difference.
Methyl chlorocarbonate	$d_{15}, 1.236$	71.4°	
Methyl fluocarbonate	$d_{33}, 1.06$	40°	31.4
Ethyl chlorocarbonate	$d_{15}, 1.144$	93°	
Ethyl fluocarbonate	$d_{33}, 1.11$	57°	36
Acetyl chloride		52° (720 mm.)	
Acetyl fluoride		20.8° (770 mm.)	31.2
Propionyl chloride		80°	
Propionyl fluoride		44°	36

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EXPERIMENTAL.

Method of Analysis.

Estimation of C and H.—The ordinary method of analysis of organic compounds is to be modified for the following reasons: (1) Organic fluocompounds heated in contact with glass yield SiF_4 which is not decomposed by CuO maintained at a dull red heat. (2) Hydrofluoric acid vapour is incompletely decomposed by CuO .

The analysis was carried out as recommended by Moissan (*Ann. chim. Phys.*, 1890, vi, 19, 277); the combustion was effected in a current of oxygen in a metal tube by means of a mixture of CuO (80%) and litharge (20%), the latter retaining all fluorine as oxyfluoride. The metal tube used in this case was a copper tube filled with the aforesaid mixture and heated to redness in an electric furnace. In order to prevent the two end corks from charring a lead tube, through which cold water was circulated, was coiled round the ends. The substance to be analysed was weighed in a capillary tube introduced into hard glass tube drawn to a capillary end and placed close to the end of the copper tube. It was then cautiously vapourised in a slow current of dry oxygen by means of a regulated tiny microburner.

Estimation of fluorine.—Generally the fluorine directly linked to carbon is extremely difficult to analyse. In these cases no such difficulty was experienced owing to the presence of a doubly linked oxygen attached to the same carbon atom.

The sealed tube containing a weighed amount of the substance was broken in 6 *N*-ammonia taken in a stoppered pyrex flask. After the completion of the hydrolysis, the solution was transferred to a platinum basin and evaporated on the water-bath to drive off the excess of ammonia. The residue was then dissolved in water, filtered and the fluorine was then precipitated as calcium fluoride with calcium nitrate. The precipitate was afterwards filtered through a tared glass gooch, washed with water saturated with calcium fluoride, dried at 120° and weighed.

Ethyl fluocarbonate.—Ethyl chlorocarbonate (35 g.) was taken in a 100 c.c. flask fitted with a condenser, cooled by iced water. Powdered anhydrous thalious fluoride (74 g.) was introduced into the flask and the mixture well shaken and left for about 12 hours at the

room temperature (27°) with occasional stirring and was then refluxed on a water-bath for 2-3 hours. The product distilled at 57° and was purified by redistillation; d_{33} , 1.06, yield, 14 g. (47% of the theory). (Found: C, 38.8; H, 5.53; F, 20.81. $C_3H_5O_2F$ requires C, 39.1; H, 5.43; F, 20.65 per cent).

It is a pungent smelling lachrymatory liquid. It reacts vigorously with ammonia with the formation of ammonium fluoride and urethane. The reaction product is treated with ether from which urethane crystallises out and is identified by its melting point.

Methyl fluocarbonate.—Methyl chlorocarbonate (25 g.) was taken in a 100 c.c. flask with a condenser fitted with ice-cold water. Anhydrous thallos fluoride (65 g.) was introduced and the mixture well shaken and kept in an ice-bath for about 6 hours. The flask was then kept at the room temperature for 2-3 hours and finally refluxed at 50°. The product distils at 40°, yield 5 g. (Found: F, 24.53. $C_2H_3O_2F$ requires F, 24.48 per cent).

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